

Research and Innovation Staff Exchange (RISE)

Call: H2020-MSCA-RISE-2017

**Heart-on-Chip based on induced pluripotent Stem Cell
Technology**
for personalized medicine

Project ID: 778354

Start date of the project: 01/01/2017

Duration: 48 months

Deliverable D3.1

Project website

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Deliverable No: 3.1 – Project website

Document Properties

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WP number	3
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Dissemination level	Public
Review status	WP leader accepted Coordinator accepted
Due Date	31 st of May 2018
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Executive summary

The report of Deliverable D3.1 generally describes the website created for external and internal communication. It presents the motivation behind the concept of the website, names the parties responsible for the website and benefiting from it, describes the content of both public and private sections, and defines the expected impact for the project consortium and the whole community.

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1. Introduction

CISTEM website is accessible at www.cistem-project.com and it will be the main tool for communication and dissemination of information related to the project. The project website will allow access to key message and information about the project. The results and research activities will be made available for the general public. The project site will present basic project information, key results, new items, event information. It will follow project's progress, secondment activities and latest news from partners, information for the media and publications (newsletter, diffusion activities). The website is hosted and maintained by the BioSense Institute. The website constitutes as the most important tool to increase project visibility and impact towards medical communities, researchers, R&D community and general public. It serves also as a tool for communication between consortium members.

2. Website content

The CISTEM website was developed and launched in January 2018. It was designed in a simple and audience accessible manner. All sections of the website have on top the CISTEM logo and a top bar with a menu depicting seven category pages are enlisted (Figure 1):

- Home (general information about CISTEM project)
- About (overview of the project and work packages)
- Consortium (partners on the project)
- News (update on the CISTEM activities)
- Communication and dissemination (photos, videos, dissemination material)
- Secondments (activities of the people on the secondments)
- Login (option available to the consortium members for the project material update)

All sections also provide addressing and contact information, appropriate acknowledgment and reference to the European Union's Horizon 2020 H2020-MSCA-RISE Program.

The **Home** page is designed to provide the viewers with the project at a glance and to attract the attention of the viewers to further explore the website content. All features of the homepage are user editable and sections can be added and removed as required during the project.

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The screenshot shows the home page of the CISTEM project website. At the top left is the CISTEM logo with the tagline 'HEART-ON-CHIP'. The navigation menu includes 'Home', 'About', 'Consortium', 'News', 'Communication and dissemination', 'Secondments', and 'Login'. Social media icons for LinkedIn, Twitter, and Facebook are on the right. A banner image shows a laboratory setting with the text 'MICROFLUIDIC TECHNOLOGY' and 'Microfluidic training at BEOnChip'. Below the banner is the main heading: 'CISTEM – HEART ON CHIP BASED ON INDUCED PLURIPOTENT STEM CELL TECHNOLOGY FOR PERSONALIZED MEDICINE'. The page contains three paragraphs of text, each starting with an icon: a magnifying glass for the first paragraph, a microscope for the second, and a person for the third. To the right of the text is a microscopic image of 'Contracting cardiomyocytes' with a credit line: 'Courtesy of Dr. Jacek Stepniewski, Department of Medical Biotechnology, Jagiellonian University in Krakow'. At the bottom, there is a dark footer with the European Union flag, funding information, and contact details for Jovana Stanojev.

CISTEM
HEART-ON-CHIP

Home About Consortium News Communication and dissemination Secondments Login in t f

MICROFLUIDIC TECHNOLOGY
Microfluidic training at BEOnChip

CISTEM – HEART ON CHIP BASED ON INDUCED PLURIPOTENT STEM CELL TECHNOLOGY FOR PERSONALIZED MEDICINE

 Many rare diseases cause chronic health problems or are even life-threatening. The majority of rare diseases are still without any effective treatment. The development of novel human systems for drug discovery therefore represents a major public health priority.

 Microfluidic technology-based "Organs-on-a-chip" represents a powerful tool for investigating rare disease mechanisms and testing new drug and treatment due to their ability to mimic tailored micro-environment architecture inspired by organ-level functions in vivo. However, due to the variability in rare disease mechanisms from one patient to another, organ on chip technology needs to be more precise and to convey towards personalized medicine.

 The human-induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs) have a strong potential in engineering organ-on-a-chip since they are derived in a patient-matched manner which makes them a superb source to construct human models for personalized drug screening as well as for understanding patient-specific fundamentals of diseases.

 To provide novel miniaturized platform for investigation of rare diseases able to address the burning issues in precision medicine today, CISTEM will bring together several research directions which are too often investigated separately at the academic level but also at the industrial level.

Contracting cardiomyocytes

Courtesy of Dr. Jacek Stepniewski, Department of Medical Biotechnology, Jagiellonian University in Krakow

 This project has received funding from H2020-MSCA-RISE-2017 programme under grant agreement No.778354

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Figure 1. Home page

The **About** section gives information about the project, the research objectives and the specific objectives of the H2020 project (Figure 2). In the Work packages section viewers can find information who is responsible for which WP, and what are the tasks determined by the work packages (Figure 3).

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CISTEM – heart on Chip based on Induced pluripotent **STEM** cell technology for personalized medicine-, is a Horizon 2020; Marie Skłodowska-Curie Research and Innovation Staff Exchange (RISE).

The CISTEM project is based on a research project integrated with a staff exchange programme designed to establish a multidisciplinary network aiming to enhance its collective research excellence and create new research training in key disciplines that will support the provision of novel organ-on-chip.

Through cross-cutting activities, the CISTEM project brings together many key players from academia and private sector of Europe and beyond to develop a novel "heart on chip" platform based on iPSCs that may be highly valuable platforms for personalized and precision medicine and therapeutics.

Organ on a chip is a 3D microfluidic cell culture chip that stimulates the activities and physiological response of entire organs. It is a type of artificial organ. This technology can be implemented on various organs. CISTEM project will be oriented on developing heart on a chip for investigating Duchenne muscular dystrophy.

Courtesy of Cherry Biotech

Figure 2. About page

WP number	WP title	Lead beneficiary	WP leader
WP1	Heart On Chip based on human-induced pluripotent Stem cell Technology	Jagiellonian University in Krakow	Prof. Dr. Jozef Dulak
WP2	Training and networking	Elvesys	Dr. Lydie Jeux
WP3	Communication and dissemination	BioSense Institute	MSc. Jovana Stanojev
WP4	Project Management	BioSense Institute	Dr. Georges Dubourg
WP5	Ethics requirements	BioSense Institute	Dr. Georges Dubourg

WORK PACKAGE 1 (WP1)
Heart On Chip based on human-induced pluripotent Stem cell Technology
Objectives:

- Establishment of procedure for iPSC differentiation into cardiomyocytes using microfluidic and microsystem technologies
- Production of microfluidic platform for heart-on-a-chip model

WORK PACKAGE 3 (WP3)
Communication and Dissemination
Objectives:

In this WP, the CISTEM consortium will undertake specific measures designed to increase visibility of project results and support their impact by

- Raising awareness about the project results and activities.
- Carrying out professional marketing actions – digital and

Figure 3. Page about work packages

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In the **Consortium** page visitors can read about partners in the CISTEM consortium and find more about their field of expertise (Figure 4). Every partner is briefly described in terms of research quality CISTEM and people responsible for the project.

The screenshot shows the CISTEM project website's Consortium page. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links for Home, About, Consortium, News, Communication and dissemination, Secondments, and Login. Social media icons for LinkedIn, Twitter, and Facebook are also present. The main content area is divided into three columns, each representing a consortium partner:

- BioSense INSTITUTE:** Located in Serbia (Novi Sad). Website: biosense.rs. Description: Nano and Microelectronics group focuses on the development of state-of-the-art sensors for applications in agriculture, food and environmental monitoring, including electronic, microwave, optical, magnetic, biological and chemical sensors of various parameters related to plants, soil, presence of toxins, pesticides etc. Key persons: Dr. Georges Dubourg (Project Coordinator, WP Leader: Management and ethics, e-mail: georgesdubourg@uns.ac.rs) and MSc. Jovana Stanojev (WP Leader: Communication and dissemination).
- BEOnChip:** Located in Spain (Zaragoza). Website: beonchip.com. Description: BEOnChip is a start-up company focused on the field of Micro-biotechnology with experience in chips for cell culture under biomimetic conditions, which are the key technology for Organ-on-Chip systems. BEONCHIP core business is the development, production and commercialization of its own-proprietary microfluidic cell culture devices (BEONCHIP technology is protected by four patents), bearing a unique portfolio. Key person: Dr. Rosa Monge.
- Universidad Zaragoza:** Located in Spain (Zaragoza). Website: unizar.es. Description: The main goal of our research line inside AMB group is the use of computational simulation tools to help in the design and fabrication of biomimetic microfluidic devices to solve clinical relevant problems. We are interested in two different approaches, one focused in the reproduction of the cellular microenvironment using microtechnologies-microfluidics and the other focused in the study of how the mechanical stimuli of the microenvironment affect to the cellular and tissue behavior. Key persons: Dr. Ignacio Ochoa Garrido and Prof. Luis Fernandez.

Figure 4. Consortium page

The purpose of the **News** page is informing visitors about events that are organized in regards to CISTEM project (Figure 5).

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Figure 5. News page

The **Communication and dissemination page** records all the material disseminating CISTEM results. These include brochures, leaflets, press information, research papers, patents, public deliverables, and other dissemination materials provided by the consortium members (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Communication and dissemination page

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The **Secondments** page is dedicated to researchers who are going on secondments, sharing their work and experience during secondments. Also, you can find information about CISTEM training programmes and seconded people (Figure 7).

CISTEM
HEART-ON-CHIP

Home About Consortium News Communication and dissemination **Secondments** Login in

SECONDMENTS

To address the research challenges CISTEM project aims also to implement a high quality inter-sector and international staff exchange programme in order to:

- Address knowledge gaps in the use of microfluidic and microsystem technologies for precision and personalized medicine, by coupling technological advances in microtechnology and stem cell biology.
- Contribute to bridging the gap between industry and high education institutions by implementing a structured secondment-based exchange programme
- Connect high-quality research infrastructures and use them as training facilities for developing and completing the skills of the CISTEM participants.

ELVESYS Innovation Centre
Cherry Biotech
BEOnChip
Universidad Zaragoza
BioSense INSTITUTE
RUTGERS School of Engineering

▲ Non-academic
▲ Academic
▲ Third country

→ International secondments
→ Intersectoral secondments, sent from academic
→ Intersectoral secondments, sent from non-academic

Figure 7. Secondments page

The **Login** page is intended for consortium members, who are going to upload material on this website.

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3. Social media

CISTEM project is present on other social media pages, like Facebook (Figure 8), LinkedIn (Figure 9) and Twitter (Figure 10). These pages are used for dissemination of CISTEM project, for the interaction with other institutions and networking. Links to all social media pages can be found also on the website.

Figure 8. Facebook page

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Figure 9. LinkedIn page

Figure 10. Twitter page

4. Conclusions

CISTEM website is the main online tool to present and disseminate all the results and events under the framework of the project. It will be regularly updated in order to provide the latest news, events, relevant results and breakthroughs. The website is carefully designed to address the identified target groups in the most effective way, and it is the easiest way to ensure the visibility of the project for the EU as well as target audiences, consortium, stakeholders and general public. The expected outcome using an online communication includes a large number of stakeholders being more aware of ideas and technologies for organ-on-chip technology. It will also be a repository for deliverables and a work area for the project participants to share information between each other. It can be continuously improved and updated, in order to maximize the results and share the results with target audiences. What is more, other platforms, like Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, are also going to help with communication and dissemination of project material.